

BUSINESS STRATEGY PLANNING IN STATE ISLAMIC RELIGIOUS UNIVERSITY: A CASE STUDY IN UIN K.H. ABDURRAHMAN WAHID PEKALONGAN

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Abstract

The purpose of this article is to examine public service bodies in state Islamic religious universities from the aspect of business planning, a case study at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan. This study uses a combination of quantitative and qualitative method approaches. The findings of this study indicate that the commitment and consistency and high sincerity of all stakeholders in implementing policies and developing UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan in the future is very important to be maintained and maintained. Implementation of the Business Strategic Plan at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan should always be monitored and evaluated on an ongoing basis by a competent institution in his field. Based on this finding, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan as one of the State Islamic Religious Universities in Indonesia showed a significant increase. This is expected to be able to bring UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan has become a professional and strong public service agency.

Keywords: Planning, public service agencies, business and university.

Introduction

The Ministry of Religion is a ministry that has duties in two fields, namely religion and education. In any field the President and Vice President instruct to create an increase in the quality of human resources who have high competitiveness which is manifested in the Vision of the President and Vice President 2020-2024 which reads "The Realization of an Advanced Indonesia that is Sovereign, Independent and Personal, Based on Mutual Cooperation". Responding to these challenges, the Ministry of Religion's Vision was made which is contained in the Ministry of Religion's Strategic Plan as a form of concern for the achievement of the President's Vision (M. Fahri Andrianto et al., 2021).

The Ministry of Religion's vision is as follows: "A professional and reliable Ministry of Religion in building a pious, moderate, intelligent and superior society to realize an advanced Indonesia that is sovereign, independent, and has a personality based on mutual cooperation" (Aziz, 2019).

In this vision, 6 things are reflected in the Ministry of Religion's program, namely Professional, Reliable, Pious, Moderate, Intelligent, and Superior. All keywords refer to improving the quality of qualified human resources. Furthermore, a mission is made as a concrete step towards achieving the vision that has been described (Scholtes et al., 2019).

The mission of the Ministry of Religion is made by integrating the missions of the President and Vice President. The missions of the Ministry of Religion include: Improving the quality of religious piety; Strengthening religious moderation and religious harmony (Kawangung, 2019); Improving religious services that are fair, easy and equitable (Oyo-Ita et al., 2021); Improving equitable and quality education services (Rao et al., 2021); Increase the productivity and competitiveness of education (Eguia, 2022); and Strengthening good governance (Mulyany & Aida Fitri, 2021).

The formulation of the policy direction and strategy of the Ministry of Religion in achieving the vision and goals, referring to the direction of national policies and strategies by considering the potential and strategic issues of the Ministry of Religion that will be faced in the next five years (Musthofiyah et al., 2021).

The Ministry of Religion's policies and strategies for 2020-2024 are directed as follows: Improving the quality of understanding and practicing religious teachings; Improving the quality of religious moderation and religious harmony; Increasing the harmony of religious and cultural relations; Improving the quality of religious

life services; Increasing the utilization of the religious economy of the people; Improving the quality of learning and teaching. Policies in improving the quality of learning and teaching are improving the quality of students' literacy and thinking skills in Mathematics, Natural Sciences and Indonesian through learning; Improving the quality of equitable access to education; Improving the quality of management and placement of educators; Improving the quality of education quality assurance; Improving the mental quality/character of students; Improving quality higher education; Improving the quality of effective, transparent and accountable governance; Improving the quality of research, development and policy is focused on producing accurate policies (Lestari et al., 2021).

In order to realize the vision and mission, both from the President and Vice President as well as the vision and mission of the Ministry of Religion and the Directorate General of Islamic Education, the Pekalongan State Islamic Institute has a lot of potential to be able to realize the Vision and Mission of the Ministry of Religion as well as the Nawacita of the President and Vice President. To support the potential of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan needed a more flexible movement. This flexibility can be realized by implementing the Financial Management Pattern of the Public Service Agency (Nugroho et al., 2020).

Business Strategy Plan of the Public Service Agency of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan is based on applicable laws and the work program of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan to support the achievement of the vision and mission of the UIN KH work unit. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan and the Indonesian Ministry of Religion. The legal rules used to compile are as follows: Republic of Indonesia Law Number 17 of 2003 concerning State Finances, Republic of Indonesia Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, Republic of Indonesia Law Number 1 of 2004 concerning State Treasury, Law No. RI Number 15 of 2004 concerning Auditing the Responsibility and Management of State Finances, Government Regulation Number 23 of 2005 concerning Financial Management of Public Service Agencies, Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 12 of 2012 concerning Higher Education, Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 4 of 2014 concerning the Implementation of Higher Education and Management of Higher Education, Regulation of the Minister of Religion Number 42 of 2016 concerning Organization and Work Procedure of the Ministry of Religion, Regulation of the Minister of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia Number 61 of 2017 concerning Organization and Work Procedure of the Pekalongan State Islamic Institute, Presidential Regulation Number 18 of 2020 concerning Medium-Term Development Plans National Year 2020-2024, Ministerial Regulation K Finance of the Republic of Indonesia Number 129 of 2020 concerning Public Service Agencies, Regulation of the Minister of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia No. 18 of 2020 concerning the Strategic Plan of the Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia for 2020-2024 (Purwanto et al., 2020).

Based on the phenomena and data above, the researcher is interested in studying and researching public service bodies at State Islamic Religious Universities from the aspect of business planning, case studies at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, Indonesia.

Strategic Plan of the Directorate General of Islamic Education in Indonesia

Referring to the Decree of the Director General of Islamic Education Number 4475 of 2020 concerning the Strategic Plan of the Directorate General of Islamic Education for 2020 - 2024, it is stated that the direction of the Strategic Policy of the Directorate General of Islamic Education is to improve the quality of religious moderation; Improving the quality of students' literacy and thinking skills; Equitable access to quality education; Fulfillment of the number of competent and professional educators and education personnel; Increasing the accreditation rating of madrasah, religious education and religious colleges; Improving student character and creating conditions for learning culture in the education unit environment; Increasing the productivity of Islamic Religious College graduates with international reputation; and Improve the quality of effective, transparent and accountable bureaucratic reforms (Di Nauta et al., 2020).

The strategic objectives of the Directorate General of Islamic Education are improving the quality of religious moderation focused on the preparation of religious literacy, strengthening the content of religious moderation, the quality of extracurricular activities, tolerance behavior, uswah behavior of educators and education staff; Improving the quality of students' literacy and thinking skills is focused on the formation of a literacy and numeracy culture in all subjects through creative and innovative learning, and based on critical,

creative, and collaborative analysis; Increasing Access to Quality Education is focused on improving the quality of classroom capacity (sitting capacity) supported by adequate facilities and infrastructure (especially in 3T areas), withdrawing ATS in the education system, providing educational assistance, improving the quality of final year education in pre-school, taking into account gender mainstreaming; Fulfilling the number of competent and professional educators and teaching staff focused on fulfilling the number of educators and education personnel who meet competency standards, continuous professional development, improvement of welfare based on performance appraisal, equitable distribution and revitalization of Educational Personnel Education Institutes in improving the quality of graduates according to needs; Increasing the accreditation rating of madrasas, religious education and religious universities is directed at increasing the accreditation ratings of madrasas, religious education and religious universities; Improving student character and creating conditions for a learning culture in the education unit environment is focused on 18 types of national and pioneering characters, as well as creating conditions for a learning culture in the educational unit environment that supports it; Increasing the productivity of Islamic Religious College graduates who are superior and with international reputation is focused on increasing the productivity of graduates and institutions of Islamic Religious Universities that have comparative advantages and international reputations; and Improving the quality of effective, transparent and accountable bureaucratic reforms focused on the quality of effective, transparent and accountable governance services in order to maintain the Unqualified predicate in financial statement opinions and increase the value of bureaucratic reform performance (Bradford et al., 2017).

The strategic programs of the Directorate General of Islamic Education are the Management Support Program; Higher Education Programs; Teaching and Learning Quality Program; and 12-year Early Childhood Education and Compulsory Education Program (Hendri Hermawan Adinugraha & Muhtarom, 2021).

The objectives of the Directorate General of Islamic Education are to strengthen the quality of religious moderation at all levels and types of Islamic education; Increasing students who receive quality Islamic Education services; Increasing Islamic Education graduates who are productive and have comparative competitiveness; and Increasing the culture of government bureaucracy within the Directorate General of Islamic Education which is clean, serving, and responsive (Agustri & Senses, 2020).

Duties and Functions of State Islamic University: UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan Perspective

As one of the State Religious Universities under the auspices of the Directorate General of Islamic Education at the Ministry of Religion, the determination of policy directions and strategies for UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan 2020-2024 refers to the Strategic Plan of the Ministry of Religion 2020-2024 and the Strategic Plan of the Directorate General of Islamic Education 2020-2024. The direction of policies and strategies in the Strategic Plan of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan 2020-2024 strives to support the achievement of the vision of the Ministry of Religion and the Directorate General of Islamic Education, which is oriented towards the creation of quality and competitive Indonesian human resources with the foundation of internalizing religious values that are moderate, inclusive, tolerant, harmonious, non-violent, as well as respecting diversity and difference.

In the 2017-2020 Strategic Plan period, the Pekalongan State Islamic Institute laid the foundation for strengthening good, clean and service governance and building the scientific base of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan with an Indonesian perspective, as proclaimed in the Master Plan for the Development of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan 2017-2036 phase I. Taking into account the achievements of the 2017-2020 Strategic Plan program and the results of the analysis of current conditions and the policy direction of the Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia and the Directorate of Islamic Education, the UIN KH Policy Direction was formulated. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan for the next 5 years from 2020-2024 as follows: Improved access, quality and relevance; Increasing institutional capacity and competitiveness; Capacity building of human resources and infrastructure; and Development of the tri dharma of higher education based on harmonization of knowledge.

Target Business Strategy Plan in UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan

UIN KH's strategic business plan. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan for 2022-2026 contains Strategic Policies and Targets and measures of achievement or achievement indicators with reference to the 2020-2024 Strategic Plan (Adinugraha et al., 2020). The presentation of the strategic business plan of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan can be explained in the following description:

First, Policy Direction: Improving access, quality and relevance. Program Targets: Strengthening religious moderation, Increasing equitable access to quality education, Increasing the quality of education quality assurance, Strengthening gender mainstreaming. Performance Indicators: Establishment of a house of religious moderation; High religious moderation index; Number of religious moderation literacy activities; Religious moderation survey, Increasing the number of types of scholarships; Number of Scholarship recipients; Number of students from province; Country of origin (full time and part time foreign students); Percentage of UKT category I; The number of students from other universities who take part in studying at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, Number of quality assurance automation; QS version of National Level Higher Education Ranking Number of internationally accredited study programs; Number of A-accredited study programs; Number of excellent accredited study programs; Excellent PT accreditation rating 2024; Establishment of Higher Education Standards; Number of internationally accredited study programs, percentage of lactation rooms in each faculty, postgraduate, rectorate and office building (7 buildings); Rector's Decree on the formulation of policies with a gender perspective; Campus declaration of zero tolerance for gender-based violence; Separate ablution places for men and women (Kingminghae & Lin, 2019).

Second, Policy Direction: Capacity building and institutional competitiveness. Program Targets: Increased strategic cooperation and institutional competitiveness, improved mental quality/character of students, increased quality of governance, institutions that are effective, transparent, accountable, fair and responsible. Performance Indicators: Number of new undergraduate programs; Number of new master program study programs; Number of Doctoral Program Study Programs; Number of international cooperation; Amount of money coming in from cooperation, Percentage of portfolio-based selection; The availability of RPS that accommodates the four character variables; Religious Moderation Index; Availability of career and entrepreneurship development center; Total academic & non-academic achievements, organizational performance index (Scale 5); GUG Index (Scale 1-5); VMTS achievement survey; Governance Satisfaction Survey; Management Satisfaction Survey; Operational Fund per Student per Year (Darmalaksana et al., 2018).

Third, Policy Direction: Capacity building of human resources and infrastructure. Program Targets: Increasing the quality and quantity of lecturers and education staff, increasing the quality of facilities and infrastructure that are friendly to the disabled and the environment, increasing the quality of information systems and databases. Performance Indicators: Lecturer to student ratio; Number of professors; Percentage of lecturers; Certified; Percentage of lecturers with doctoral degrees, Number of lecturers per Study Program, Number of lecturers who have TOEFL more than 500, Percentage of classes that use LCD; Access the online library; e-learning, e-books, repositories, disabled facilities; Learning information system; Percentage of relevant and up-to-date infrastructure for all research and community services program organizers; The realization of learning corners; Availability of educational equipment and media; Availability of maintenance, safety and security facilities, percentage of information system development blueprints; Number of applications for administrative and financial services; Updating data through an integrated information system; Number of information systems (finance, staffing, planning, assets, research, community dedication, academic learning, tracer study). Realization of a dashboard system with a complete database (Rofiq et al., 2019).

Fourth, Policy Direction: Development of higher education tri dharma based on harmonization of knowledge. Program Targets: Increasing the quality of education services and the quality of graduates, Increasing the quality and quantity of research and scientific publications, increasing the quality and quantity of community service. Performance Indicators: Curriculum review, Service quality survey; Procurement of digital reference sources; Percentage of lecturers who use portfolio assessment; Student involvement in lecturer research, research roadmap documents are available; Percentage increase in research budget; Number of lecturer research titles; Number of publications; Number of lecturer citations; Number of IPRs;

Number of research funding collaborations, available service roadmap; state university operational assistance percentage; Number of lecturers who have received competitive service (Dent, 2015).

Implementation of the Business Strategic Plan in UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan

With the completion of the preparation of the UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan within the next 5 (five) years, it requires commitment and consistency as well as high sincerity from the leadership of the institute, faculties, study programs, institutions, centers, technical support units, bureaus, divisions, and the Sub-Sections in implementing policies and development of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan in the future. It is hoped that this Business Strategic Plan can be broken down into a Budget Business Plan at the level of faculties, study programs, institutions, bureaus, and technical support units (Zhou & Tang, 2020).

The operations of this Strategic Business Plan are realized in the form of a Budget Business Plan which will be prepared at the institute, faculty, agency, bureau, and technical support units level. The Budget Business Plan is an operational document that includes the planning and budgeting process and the action plan. Therefore, before submitting a budget to the Ministry of Religion, the Budget Business Plan has been formulated first. Thus, the budget for activities or educational programs listed in the DIPA is an elaboration of the Budget Business Plan and the Business Strategic Plan, so that the education budget sourced from the APBN is clear and the level of achievement is measurable (Sirat, 2010).

Furthermore, the implementation of the Business Strategic Plan and Budget Business Plan at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will be monitored and evaluated on an ongoing basis by the Quality Assurance Institute and the Internal Supervisory Unit. The results of monitoring and evaluation will be reported to the Chancellor as a performance accountability report for UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan both yearly and five years. This report will also be published on the official website of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, so that it can be accessed and read by all stakeholders, both internal and external stakeholders as a strategy to build a positive image of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan in the eyes of the public (Jailani & Adinugraha, 2022).

Finally, so that it can be used as a reference for all parties involved in the implementation of higher education at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, the contents of this Business Strategic Plan have been socialized to all stakeholders, with the aim of building commitment from all internal stakeholders in carrying out the programs and activities that have been formulated in this Business Strategic Plan document; Provide the same and in-depth understanding of the work program that must be achieved by each line at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan in order to achieve the vision, mission, and educational goals that have been developed by UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan himself; Building the same paradigm in implementing the program and increasing appreciation of the content and substance of the UIN KH Business Strategic Plan. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan; Develop a culture that is conducive and responsive to the planned changes to be achieved by UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, so that all stakeholders are able and willing to understand, accept, and support the existence of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan became the best university.

Conclusion

The findings of this study indicate that the commitment and consistency and high sincerity of all stakeholders in implementing policies and developing UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan in the future is very important to be maintained and maintained. Implementation of the Business Strategic Plan at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan should always be monitored and evaluated on an ongoing basis by a competent institution in his field. A concrete example of the implementation of the planning is, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan uses a variety of recruitment systems that are able to provide opportunities for prospective students from various backgrounds, both in terms of regions throughout the archipelago, academic ability, economic background, religion and physical limitations.

New student recruitment system at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan is very strict. This provides an opportunity for UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan to have really qualified students. Quantitatively, the number of new students at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan has an annual increase of around 20-25%.

In addition to providing education in the classroom, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan also has a variety of extracurricular activities for students, career guidance services and job information as a means to facilitate them in applying their knowledge in society. UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan is very active and excels in various national and international events.

Based on the findings above, it discusses the internal objective conditions which include service performance, financial performance, performance of educators and education staff, performance of facilities and infrastructure and measurement of performance achievement at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan showed a significant increase. This is expected to be able to bring UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan has become a professional and strong public service agency.

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